

Pedagogical Approach of Enhancing Speaking Skills in EFL Classroom

Research Article

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Publication Details

Received: April 25, 2024 **Accepted:** May 15, 2024 **Published:** June 30, 2024

Abstract

This study explores the concept of enhancing students' speaking skills and its beneficial impact on communicative competence (CoCo). By investigating the positive impact of classroom interaction as well as other (what other be specific) approaches for improving students' speaking proficiency. The study aims to enhance students' oral proficiency, develop strategies that align with their speaking abilities and level of achievement, and promote interaction among students, the teacher, and the course material. Based on the findings of this study, it is hypothesized that creating effective interaction in the classroom will greatly contribute to the teaching process and lead to increased speaking proficiency among learners.

Keywords: oral proficiency, achievement, beneficial, communicative competence (CoCo), classroom interaction

Chapter One

The English language is not the first language of Nepal, so Nepalese learners have to face many obstacles to acquiring the English language. In the context of Nepal, learning English is increasingly popular. Almost 95% of people require English for various purposes such as career development, exchanging information with native speakers, etc. To acquire the English language, the communicative approach (skills) is one of the most indispensable for humans to interact with one another as social beings and in personality development. The Communicative Approach – or Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) – is a teaching approach that highlights the importance of authentic communication for learning to take place. In the Communicative Approach, honest communication and interaction is the objective of learning and the means through which it takes place. The Communicative Approach aimed at developing the learner's competence to communicate in the target language with an enhanced focus on real-life situations.

The English language has been used to exchange feelings, views, and knowledge in many parts of Nepal. The study's primary purpose is to show the relationship between effective strategies and enhancing speaking skills. In addition, the study will show us that using various techniques in teaching speaking as a foreign is not a passive action. It is a very active, vital process and an important part that plays a significant role in motivating people to speak. This paper will have a lot of advantages for working language teachers, schools, teacher trainers, learning teachers, educators and policymakers. Undoubtedly, every research work carried out systematically has abundant significance to the concerned institutions, authorities and people. More than this, researchers carried out a lot of advantages for working language teachers, schools, teacher trainers, learning teachers, educators and policymakers since it will be carried out based on the genuine problematic issues in teaching and learning English in the EFL context, like in Nepal.

Further, it will also support the teacher and the material developer to develop the instructional materials with the condition of the students in mind. Similarly, a good teacher can make his/ her teaching-learning process exciting and fun by using various effective techniques to enhance his/her students' speaking skills. Using those techniques helps the teacher to explain lessons and to motivate students more and more. Hence, our present research shows that using effective strategies in teaching English is a vital process to engage students in developing their level of learning English, certainly speaking skills.

Speaking skills are one of the important factors among the four language skills that teachers should help students acquire the English language. Teachers should create communicative situations in the classroom through various activities to help them communicate in real-life situations in their daily lives. Similarly, classroom interaction is also necessary and helpful in enhancing students'

communicative skills. Interaction, such as teacher-learner and learner-learner interactions, involves a verbal exchange between learners and teachers. Likewise, the presentation also helps learners to improve their speaking ability because to make their presentation, they prepare first before deliberating their production; as a result, they can increase their vocabulary and produce their own sentences and phrases. Similarly, other effective techniques such as picture description, sharing opinions, group work, individual work, and information gaps allow students to be involved in speaking activities; as a result, students can build up their confidence and habit of speaking English in the classroom besides that, there are other methods which help the learner to produce their own sentences such as role play, storytelling, jigsaw activities, discussion methods, picture description etc. speaking skills also helps for developing listening skills. Therefore, teachers should know that the learners must do most of the time to activate their speaking since speaking skills require practice and exposure.

Therefore, many teachers find practical situations or activities to eliminate or reduce difficult situations while speaking, so learners must deal with them in the classroom. For example, if the teacher involves them in group or pair work, it might help students be more confident because their friend supports them, and they can express their feelings without hesitation. In addition, teachers should encourage them rather than pointing out their mistakes so they will learn from those errors and be encouraged to talk in the classroom by participating many times without any shyness or fear. Technology is an excellent way to make students speak at the school. Students find it more accessible and enjoyable to learn using computers or the internet. So, the teacher has to apply various methods, approaches, and techniques in the classroom to allow students to express their thoughts easily by using effective materials such as laptops, DVDs, and computers. Consequently, various strategies, such as storytelling, group work, pair work, video, picture description, etc., allow students to speak English in the classroom. So, teachers must use these activities according to their level, age, and interest to enhance students' speaking skills by using effectual materials.

1. Introduction

English language is not our first language so; Nepalese learners have to face many obstacles to acquire English language. In context of Nepal, learning English is increasing popular. Almost 95% students require English language for various purposes such as careers development, exchanging information with native speakers, etc. In order to acquire English language, Communicative skills is one of the most indispensable for human interact with one another as a social being as well as personality development. English language has been used as medium of exchanging their feeling, views, knowledge in many private schools of Nepal. Likewise, in many schools they give high priority in English language but they failed to use English language properly while communicating. If students are not confidence in speaking in English, they cannot ask questions as well as they cannot participate in language learning effectively. Therefore, teachers should involve students in speaking activities according to their age, level and interest, which helps learners to become self-confidence as well as develop their habit for speaking skills.

In similar vein, English is thought to be one of the most important languages in the world. In teaching skills there are four micro skills i.e., listening, speaking, reading and writing. Among them, speaking skills is one of the major one. All of the four macro English skills, speaking seem to be the most important skill required for communication (Carbajal & López de Ascencio, 2015). There are many reasons why English is so important. One of the reasons is that English is spoken as the first Language in many countries. Speaking is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing and receiving and processing information (Yasin et al., 2024). Therefore, English language has rapidly become the main medium of communication at home, in school, and in communal domain both locally and globally. Similarly, the use of English as an international language plays a significant role in globalization era. This means, speaking is the most important skill in acquisition of any language and their assessment in their progress in learning a language is in terms of their accomplishments in oral skills (Derseh et al., 2024). At the present time, we are required to be able to communicate in English. Meanwhile, in the context of Nepal, almost all of the private schools adopt English as a medium of instruction. The objective of teaching and learning English is to bring up students to better understanding and ability of the language. However, students are seemed to require for achieving certain score in order to pass. So, in English learning not only grammatical aspects are important but also are communicative ones. It is stated that in the English curriculum students' materials must be based on communicative skills acceptable for students' daily needs. Similarly, effective techniques such as jigsaw activities, interaction between teachers as well as students, picture description, group work etc. can be the effective teaching techniques which teachers should follow to enhance students speaking skills.

1.1 Problem of the Nepalese classroom

What we have observed about ourselves when we were in our schooling that the most of the friends of the class felt difficult to speak English in the classroom due to lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, lack of habit beside that we were afraid of making mistake, few students who spoke English and they also tended to use inappropriate grammar due to lack of habit. Similarly, students of the English classroom learn English just for marks not for developing their communicative skills. Although, students of EFL classroom are good in reading and writing, they seem reluctant to communicate with their friends as well as with their teachers in English due to lack of habit as well as self- confidence. Teachers are not much interested or may be unaware about effective techniques to improve their speaking skills. They consider reading and writing are more indispensable rather than speaking as a result they do not give high priority on speaking. Therefore, students cannot be able to express their authentic views, opinions, thoughts with others as well as they compel to be limit in narrow premises in the English environment (Narueprempree, 2024). Almost all of the school put a lot of emphasis on reading and writing due to its importance in answering the examination. This is the norm found in exam curriculum that focuses on passing examination for future undertaking.

As a result, of neglecting the most important speaking skill in English language by not providing the pupils with enough space to practice and use the language effectively has led them to encounter difficulties in conversing well in English language. Similarly, in Nepal most of the school as well as teacher did not much focus on English speaking activities as a consequence, students may think that English class is boring caused by lack of motivation- related engagement from the teacher during speaking session. In similar vein, the other problem came from the teacher he/she has still used monotonous activity in teaching and learning process. The teacher always used imitation and repetition techniques all the time. This activity made teaching and learning process is not interested to the students. Backlund (1990) assigns three area of knowledge that influences oral communication effectiveness: social knowledge, self- knowledge and content knowledge (Hamid et al., 2024; Johan et al., 2024). If anyone of this weak oral communication will be impaired. Therefore, in order to enhance students speaking skills teachers should use various effective techniques where students get chance to produce their verbal sentences. Much time for students speaking time in the EFL classroom helps pupils to increase their habit as well as self- confidence.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

As we all know that the students of Nepalese community school as well as some private students are weak in speaking in English compare than the students of private school where teachers use various activities to enhance their speaking skill. In the context of Nepal most schools put less emphasis on reading and writing due to its importance in the examinations. Most of the learners learn English Language for purposes of passing examination not necessarily for the advancement of the basic communicative skills. Although, the Nepalese curriculum equally focused on all four language skills, listening and speaking are neglected by learners and teachers as a result, learners are not be able to use English language for real life situation in their daily life. In similar vein, especially those running in Nepali medium even in some private school of students are found to have low level of their confidence while communicating in English with both teachers and students. Through my experience of teaching English as a foreign language, we have realized that several pedagogical issues have been barriers to teaching and learning English. Among these, lack of self-confidence as well as lack of habit during speaking has become the major problems in speaking English. Since, the main purpose of learning English language is for communication, students need to build the level of self-confidence and habit for communication (Wu & Tarc, 2021). So, teacher is the first priority who can build up their self-confidence and develop their habit by involving them in different activities according to their level, age, interest.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to show relationship between the effective strategies as well as enhancing students speaking skill. In addition to, the study will show us that using various techniques in teaching speaking as a foreign is not passive actions. It is very active it is vital process and an important part that play great role in motivating students in speaking.

1.4 Research Question

The study sought the answer the following research questions:

1. What are the techniques used by the teachers to enhance students Speaking English?
2. In what ways do EFL teachers use those techniques to improve their speaking skills?

1.5 Rational

This paper will have a lot of advantages for working language teacher, schools, teacher trainer, learning teacher, educators and policy makers. With no doubt, every research work carried out systematically has abundant significances to the concerned institutions, authorities and its people. More than this, we as researcher carried out the this research to have a lot of advantages for working language teachers, schools, teacher trainers, learning teachers, educators and policy makers since it is going to be carried out based on the very real problematic issues in teaching and learning English as EFL context like in Nepal. Further, it will also be supporting to the teacher as well as material developer to develop the instructional materials with the condition of the students in mind. Similarly, a good teacher can make his/ her teaching learning process interesting and fun by using various effective techniques in order to enhance his/her students speaking skills. Using those techniques helps the teacher to explain lessons and to motivate students more and more. Hence, in our present research aim to show that using effective techniques in teaching English is vital process to engage students for developing their level in learning English certainly speaking skill.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Thematic Review

2.1.1 Speaking

Generally, communication can be defined as a process of exchanging information, from the person giving the information through verbal and non-verbal methods, to the person receiving the information. Communication also involves the exchange of ideas, opinions and information with a specific objective. Apart from oral communication, information can also be exchanged using symbols or sign. Communication has also been defined as sharing and giving meaning occurring at the same time through symbolic interactions (Abeid et al., 2024). Communication has been said to start when a message or information is transferred from the sender (the speaker, writer) to the receiver (listener, reader) through an instrument or channel, and followed by the receiver giving feedback coding and interpreting the information added by Sulaiman Masri (1997) and Vianingrum and Setyowati (2021).

Based on these definitions, elements of communication include the person giving the information, the information and feedback by the receiver, and the repetition of these processes creates knowledge development. University students need to be given opportunities to communicate in order to be better prepared for the job market after their studies. Communication is more effective if the receiver (of the information) can understand and practice the skills. Further, communication will be more meaningful if the physical, spiritual and social factors are taken into account during the communication process. As a university student who is getting ready to start on their chosen career, he or she should take the opportunity in any activities that developed communication skills in a wider and complete aspect so that communication skills can be fully developed. Students need to put in effort to develop their communication skills to be able to succeed in their chosen profession (Swargiary, 2024). There are many types of communication skills, but generally it involves oral and written skills.

Mohd Helmwe (2005) proposes that there are essentially three types of communication, which are interpersonal communication, management communication (communication in a group), and public communication (speech making) (Pavón-Guinea & Codina, 2024). The process of communication generally involves four elements, which are the speaker, the receiver, communication channel and feedback. A few researchers have defined communication as verbal communication, written communication, non-verbal communication, listening and giving feedback (Iksan et al., 2012). As we believe that communication as a non-verbal skill, giving feedback, presenting ideas verbally and in written form, doing presentations and negotiating to achieve a goal and getting support/agreement. In our globalized world, University students need to master in communicating skills in different cultural context. Hence, universities must provide many more activities to develop the students' communication skills in order to meet the challenges of the globalized world. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the level of communication skills (oral, written and social skills) among local university students (Abdi et al., 2024).

Learners need to be able to interact with other people. This involves a wide range of skills. First of all, they need to think of something to say in the second language and feel confident enough to try to express it. Then they have to put words, phrase and sentences together. Using grammar and vocabulary to express what they want to say in a way that others can understand. They have to be able to vocalize this using pronunciation and intonation in a way that is clear enough to keep up the flow of conversation they need to be reasonable fluent. They may also have to stretch the language they know to cope with new situation: instead of hesitating to search for a word they have forgotten or don't know, they need to be able to find another way of expressing their meaning. Interaction involves more than just putting a message together: it involves responding to other people (Eilan, 2020). This means choosing language that is appropriate for the person you are talking to you. It means responding to what they say, taking turns in a conversation, encouraging them to speak, and expressing interest, changing the topic asking them to repeat or explain what they are saying and so on.

2.1.2 How to help learners develop their speaking skills?

We can help learners speak by helping them to find ideas and supporting them so they feel confident enough to speak. We can give them opportunities to practice enough to become fluent, and we can get them to improvise and stretch the language that they know to cope with a range of different situations. We can give them opportunities to interact with others and help them with useful phrases and expressions for turn-taking, changing the topic, expressing interest etc.

In order to enhance students speaking there are various strategies such as reduce TTT, increase STT, avoiding Yes/ No questions, activities such as group discussion/ debate (topic must be of students interest) description of place/ things/ people in pairs for guessing etc which helps every teacher to make their classroom interactive as well as communicative based as a result we as teacher can be successful to produce good English speaker. These types of activities tend to help students speak English in the classroom.

Hymn's (1972) communicative competence was a definition of what speaker needs to know in order to be communicatively competent in speech community (Chomsky, 2011). Noam Chomsky is taken as a founder of communicative language teaching. He has used the word communicative in 1960s in the explanation of Generative Grammar. During his speech, he stated that the interaction is the mean and ultimate goal of communicative activities. In a similar token, though there is not a watertight demarcation to make activities communicative however, some of the basic principles which may guide us to make our teaching activities communicative. The term "communicative activity" refers to an activity where students display both their concrete performance and abstract knowledge while keeping in mind their needs and circumstances. In a same spirit, educational activities ought to address students' interests and global needs in order to be communicative. The activities must be interactive because interaction is the means and goal of communicative tasks. Yes, apart from these we can add that, the activities should be the interaction based and the students based.

2.1.3 Techniques used by the teachers in the classroom to enhance students English speaking skills

There are various techniques which used by the teachers in the classroom in order to enhance students' oral skills. According to Sinclair (2001) picture is defined as a visual representation or image that is painted drawn, or photographs, and rendered on a flat surface. The main advantages of a picture are its oblivious visibility to learners. Using picture can bring benefits to teaching, as they promote learners' interest in acquiring a foreign language. Byrne (1980) states that picture can stimulate students' discussion and interpretation of the topic (Turuta, 2021). Moreover, students' imaginations can also be inspired (Moore, 1982) for example, it is assumed that visual aids in general especially picture and colorful posters could add attractiveness to the atmosphere of the classroom (Tsouganatou, 2024). According to Brown (2004), the picture-cued technique can be

considered an important and powerful method to elicit students' oral language performance at extensive and intensive levels (Tequis Ibutjes, 2022).

Based on Brown's teaching principles, extensive and intensive forms of instruction may lead to monologues and rhymes respectively, where learners go over certain forms of the language. Furthermore, he states that describing pictures can be an ideal activity to begin the class because learners focus on content. In addition, they are likely to learn new topical or content vocabulary and grammar through teacher scaffolding during this activity. Moreover, they can be used to enhance students' participation and create a positive attitude towards English. All of these models are highly recommended to develop students' ability in getting better communication skills. As a result, students will be more able to prepare themselves to participate in the future of their social life and will have proficient skills. It was suggested by Raptou (2002, p. 211) that "information gap is a useful activity in which one person has information that the other lacks. All of the speakers must use the target language to share the missing information" (Almira et al., 2017, p.135-143).

For instance, a student has the directions to a party and he must give them to a classmate. One type of speaking activity involves the so-called, information gap – where two speakers have different parts of information making up a whole. Because they have different information, there is a "gap" or "information gap". Getting students to have a discussion like having them to take part to give information without a gap will bring the students into a new situation. Students will benefit from this type of learning environment by feeling more at ease and able to communicate in the target language. By using the storytelling method, students are introduced to new words, idioms, and pronunciations that they will need for oral output. Besides, storytelling method empowers and motivates learners to improve their speaking skill by presenting a tool that is less used in Nepal in English classes.

2.1.4 Materials used by the Teachers to Enhance Students' Communicative Skills

Appropriate learning materials are important in order to help students improve their speaking skills. The materials should give students a lot of opportunities to practice their English and to learn English. The materials should also be relevant to the objectives of the learning. The materials should be effective in helping the students reach the expected outcome. It is important to have various materials from many sources so that the learning process can be enjoyable, interesting, meaningful, and the students will not be bored in joining the class. Through the observation, the materials used during the class were not various. The students were not equipped with any course book. Instead, the teacher gave some hand-outs to the students. The hand-outs were related to the materials that they learnt in that meeting. The handed-outs contained the written exercises and the speaking tasks. The students usually have different hand-outs in every meeting. It is expected that the students will be curious about the materials and tasks that they have to accomplish, so that they will be more challenged.

Media, equipment's and facilities are necessary in order to optimize the learning process. Those are also used to help the learning process become easier and more effective. There are some media which are commonly used in the class, such as pictures, cards, pictures, recordings and videos. There is also some equipment to optimize the learning process such as whiteboard, laptop, DVD and many others. Others materials include such as library, story books, magazines which help learners to practice their English by discussing various topics. In order to enhance students speaking skills teachers used various effective materials so that, they can involve in speaking activities as a result they become good English speaker.

2.1.5 Communicative Language Teaching

Having good communication skills is important. They can help us with presentation in the class during job interviews, when handling arguments and in variety of another situation. There are various ways of develop communicative skills which helps learners come across as more friendly and confident. Such as be confident while speaking, more and more practice, making eye contact, use gesture for meaningful communication, use the right words and pronunciations etc.

2.1.6 Communicative Language Teaching as a Theoretical Tool

The Communicative Approach – or Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) – is a teaching approach that highlights the importance of real communication for learning to take place. In the Communicative Approach, real communication and interaction is not only the objective in learning, but also the means through which it takes place. The Communicative Approach aimed at developing the learner's competence to communicate in the target language with an enhanced focus on real-life situations.

According to Jack C. Richards, a learner can develop communicative competence by: This change has had a huge impact on classroom materials, course books, teaching techniques and the teacher's role in the classroom, and still influences English language teaching and learning up to this day. This is desirable when adopting the Communicative Approach because it seems more realistic: in genuine communication, skills are seldom employed in isolation, and an integrated-skills approach simulates what happens in real life (Manchishi, 2024). The source of the texts in skills lessons is also important. In the Communicative Approach, authentic texts are usually favored, as they might provide learners with exposure to a more genuine use of language.

Communicative language teaching focus on learners' communicative competence, it is important to provide a range of practice activities. It helps learners to involve in natural communication in their daily life situation. This method also claims to encourage learners to incorporate their personal experiences into their language learning environment, and to focus on the learning experience in addition to the learning of the target language. CLT approaches helps teachers to choose effective classroom activities for students developing communicative abilities in the target

language (Jiang & Paulino, 2024). CLT much focus on oral activities as opposed to grammar drills or reading and writing because they include active conversation and creative, unpredicted responses from students. Similarly, this theory helps learners to promote their collaboration fluency and comfort in the English language. As the teacher is not the centre of instruction anymore, activities in the Communicative Approach usually favor student-student interaction and maximize learners' opportunities to speak. Learners can practice language skills through role-playing, information gap exercises, jigsaw puzzles, open-ended discussions, and other activities. Depending on the lesson's objective, stage, and student proficiency, different levels of support may be provided. Nevertheless, it is important to stress that preparing students to perform tasks is a vital step for the successful completion of activities and the development of their communicative competence.

In this vein, we believed towards communicative language teaching approach provide learners with real communicative context. Instructors can create authentic scenarios in which students can share authentic information, allowing language to adapt to the circumstances. More opportunities for students to create and utilize the language in authentic settings foster habit development and self-confidence in learners, which enables teachers to help non-native English speakers become proficient speakers of the language. Similarly, in a classroom where the CLT approach is used, communicative activities like role playing, teacher-student contact, group activities, individual activities, and discussion presentations are helpful. Therefore, CLT approach is based on communication on real life situation in students' daily life where students have direct contact with language via various effective techniques so, students can learn English and they can use and produce English language appropriately.

2.1.7 Previous Studies

According to (Kagan, 1994) three activities such as group discussion, role play and debate adopted the learning together approach of cooperative learning, which aims to unite several different groups of individuals to form a community of practice that works to improve the academic ability of the group. He concluded that these three activities improve learners' thinking, listening and speaking skills.

In terms of second language acquisition, a learning-together strategy makes it possible for educators and learners to connect and learn more about their respective responsibilities in assisting students' English language learning. The activities that follow are highly structured characteristics in cooperative learning activities because (a) teachers design these activities for students after fully considering students' oral English proficiency and other related elements and divide students into proper groups; (b) during students' cooperative learning activities, teachers would observe and assist students' learning process and (c) at the end of the activities, teachers would most likely give some evaluation of the students' performance as well as encourage each group to provide evaluation for students' performance on both spoken English learning and cooperative skills.

Holt and Kysilka (2006) state that role play technique can be fun and lead to develop learning, these techniques can be used a student communication, they help EFL students to comprehend the importance of cooperation and to have an interest in learning. Role play is very important in teaching speaking because it gives students an opportunity to practice communicating speaking in different social contexts and in different social roles. Wright (1989) goes on to say that the use of pictures can stimulate and motivate students in language learning. When learning a second or foreign language, what learners concentrate on is grammar and phonology. Thus, Wright also states that the use of pictures provides motivation and the nonverbal stimulus that make students understand better. Wright (1989) presents a compelling argument in saying that pictures help both teachers and students, since they provide motivation to students when it comes to speaking or writing.

Sitepu and Sugito (2021) carried out research on topic students enhancing communicative skills through problem posing and presentation. They added that presentation skills are vital to achieving success in all aspects of daily life. Presentation should incorporate these four basic elements: (a) statement ideas clearly, (b) explain ideas, (c) support ideas with evidence from other sources, (d) conclude/restate ideas. Therefore, students need to be trained providing self-reflection regarding their own presentation and giving feedbacks another group oral presentation is crucial to prepare themselves to compete in the competitive environment especially communications skills. Peer evaluations and instructional rubrics are examples of proven pedagogy that may be used in conjunction with easily accessible technology, such as video hosting services, to assist students enhance their presenting skills and professional speaking talents. Therefore, the most effective methods for improving students' speaking abilities are role-play elicitation, group work, storytelling, simulation, and dialogues. If English language learners are given the aforementioned possibilities, such as role plays, dialogues, and group projects, they can improve their speaking skills in a variety of ways that will benefit EFL learners.

3. Discussion and Finding

Speaking skills is one of the important factors among four language skills which we as teacher should help students to acquire English language. Teachers should create communicative situations in the classroom through various activities to help them to communicate in their real-life situation in their daily life. Similarly, classroom interaction is also necessary and useful as enhancing students' communicative skills. Interaction such as teacher- learner interaction learner-learner interaction, which involves verbal exchange between learners and teachers. Similarly, giving presentations enables students to enhance their speaking skills since they must prepare in advance and deliberate over their content. This allows them to expand their vocabulary and formulate original words and phrases. Similar to this, there are other useful strategies that help students produce their own sentences in the classroom, like role play, storytelling, jigsaw activities, picture description, and discussion techniques. These strategies also allow students to participate in speaking activities and help them develop the confidence and habit of speaking English. Having

good speaking abilities also aids in improving listening abilities. Therefore, teachers should know that the learners need to do most of the time to activate their speaking, since speaking skills require practice and exposure.

4. Conclusion

Speaking is the most important aspect in communication, yet students have had difficulties developing their capacity in speaking. Therefore, teacher should be careful while teaching English language they have to follow effective ways to develop his/her students speaking. In the classroom many learners are not feeling easy to speak due to their shy nature they might afraid or pressured by the classmates or the teachers. As a result, a lot of teachers research effective scenarios or exercises to remove or lessen challenging situations that students may encounter in the classroom. When a teacher assigns group or pair work, for instance, it could boost students' confidence since they have a friend who encourages them to express their emotions without fear.

Teachers ought to support their students instead of calling attention to their mistakes, as this would help them grow from their mistakes and become more confident and fearless when speaking up in class. It seems that using technology in the classroom encourages children to speak. Using computers or the internet to learn is more convenient and fun for students. So there are variety of methods and approaches and techniques that the teacher has to apply in the classroom in order to allow students to express their thoughts easily in the class by using effective materials such as laptop, DVD, computer. Therefore, there are various strategies such as storytelling, group work, pair work, video, picture description etc. which allow students to speak English in the classroom. So, teachers have to use these activities according to their level, age, interest in order to enhance students speaking skill in the classroom by using effectual materials.

Funding: This study was not funded in any shape or form by any party.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Bio-Note:

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